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Predicting the likelihood of resubmission (T_1) after first failure at T_0 : A model for broadening the role of peer review for ECRs

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Introduction

The peer review system is an important mechanism for the support and fostering of academic careers, especially in the early stages (McAlpine, 2020). Previous studies of the use of peer review for the allocation of competitive funding agencies have concentrated on questions of efficiency and how to make the ‘best’ decision (van den Besselaar & Sandström, 2015), by ensuring that successful applicants are also the more productive or visible in the long term (Wang et al, 2019). By examining the patterns of resubmission for ECR applicant following an unsuccessful application, this paper in progress examines the potential peer review may play as a developmental and participatory research governance tool, rather than solely a tool for providing summative evaluations. In addition, by understanding the pattern of resubmission, this paper outlines the possibility of for further analysing how signals received as feedback via peer review reports influence the likelihood that an unsuccessful applicant would submit a future application.

Methods

The study employed a survey of unsuccessful from funding opportunities provided by the Wellcome Trust for the years 2009-2019 (n= 4105).

The funding calls used in this project were chosen because they are designed specifically to provide ECR researchers opportunity to develop their research careers post-PhD and move towards research independence. These included 4 ECR funding calls for medical research: (1) Sir Henry Wellcome Postdoctoral Fellowship; (2) Sir Henry Dale Fellowship; (3) Research Career Development Fellowship; and (4) Clinical Research Career Development Fellowship; and 1 ECR funding call for the Humanities and Social Sciences: Research Fellowships in Humanities and Social Sciences. All funding calls were open over the study period 2009-2019).

The survey asked participants questions about their initial application to the Wellcome Trust (T_0), and then to provide information submission and funding agency details from subsequent applications ($T_1 \dots T_x$) following an unsuccessful application at T_0 (outlined in Figure 1). Since The Wellcome Trust restricts the number of applications received from each UK institution for each funding call, institutions engage in several rounds of internal review and selection for applications. Due to this internal selection process, it can be assumed that all applications eventually submitted to The Wellcome Trust for consideration were high- and potentially-fundable quality. Therefore the reasons for non-selection of applications were not due to a 'lack' of excellence.

A 5-point Likert scale was used to collect respondents' perceptions of the value of the feedback received via the peer-review reports provided by the Wellcome after the outcome of the funding round were announced. In addition, applicants were asked to what extent the feedback received from Wellcome was used to guide significant changes to subsequent funding applications made by the participant during the period 2009-2019. In circumstances where participants noted that they did not pursue any further grant applications, the reason was requested and, where possible, was followed up in the interview stage of the methodology (reported elsewhere). Demographic information was also collected including a list of publications or publishing names of participants.

Figure 1. Research design of initial application (T_x) and subsequent re-applications ($T_1, 2 \dots x$)

A total of $n=400$ participants started the survey, with $n=233$ completing the survey in full. Unless indicated otherwise, the analysis utilised completed survey responses only. This response rate was lower than anticipated (9.7% and 5.7% respectively), but it was noted that the timeline for the survey completion spanned the disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic during 2020. This may have resulted to the high number of respondents who did not complete the survey in full.

Results

Patterns of re-application among unsuccessful candidates

Figure 2A shows the success and reapplication patterns of those individuals who completed the whole survey ($n=233$) including both the proportion and number of applicants who made a further funding application after T_0 . Of the 233 surveyed, 47% were successful at T_0 and did not reapply at T_1 . Reapplications were future grant applications to any funding agency, not just a reapplication to a Wellcome Trust funding call. Irrespective of the outcome at T_0 , 66% ($n=126$) reapplied for funding at T_1 . Specifically, of those unsuccessful at T_0 , 62 (50%) of respondents went on to reapply at T_1 . A total of 35% of respondents were successful at T_1 following an unsuccessful outcome at T_0 .

A diminishing pattern of resubmission was found for subsequent rounds of resubmission (T_{1+x}), as respondents were successful at earlier stages and therefore did not need to reapply for funding, or else switched to a different research topic and/or career strategy. At T_2 , 27 respondents reported reapplying which represented 68% of those who were unsuccessful at T_1 with this decrease continuing with subsequent reapplications. Although these numbers show

the number of individuals reapplying decreasing with each application stage, there is no clear pattern of reapplication suggesting a role for other motivating factors.

Figure 2. A: The number and proportion of applicants who made further applications after T₀. Figure 2. B: Applicant perception of the value of feedback received from the Wellcome Trust at T₀ as a proportion of all applicants.

A diminishing pattern of resubmission was found for subsequent rounds of resubmission (T_{1+x}), as respondents were successful at earlier stages and therefore did not need to reapply for funding, or else switched to a different research topic and/or career strategy. At T₂, 27 respondents reported reapplying which represented 68% of those who were unsuccessful at T₁ with this decrease continuing with subsequent reapplications. Although these numbers show the number of individuals reapplying decreasing with each application stage, there is no clear pattern of reapplication suggesting a role for other motivating factors.

Figure 2A outlines how both successful and unsuccessful applicants perceived the value of the feedback received. From the survey, a total of n=335 respondents answered the feedback questions. Not all applicants, successful or unsuccessful, received feedback at T₀ (n=24 (7%)). For applicants who did receive feedback, a higher proportion of successful applicants rated the feedback as extremely valuable (n=68 (51%)) when compared to unsuccessful applicants (n=18 (<10%)).

Patterns of re-application among unsuccessful candidates

Unique applicant IDs were used to first identify individuals, and then progressive applications made by the same individual over time. Of the total number of observations (n=4328), n=223 applications were identified as being 'withdrawn' or 'terminated' and were excluded from analysis, as were a further n=243 due to anonymity¹. Since the analysis was focused on the incidence of reapplication between T₀ and T₁ (other reasons, beyond the measurement of this study may underpin reasons for reapplication at T_{1+x} following an unsuccessful application at T₁), 59 further proposals were excluded as they represented the reapplication at T₂, T₃ and T₄.

This resulted in a final database of n=3389 unique individuals (applicants) and n=3803 events (reapplications at T₁). The larger number of events than individuals is due to applicants submitting more than one application at T₁, or else submissions for extensions for further funding from Wellcome by applicants successful at T₀ which were not excluded from analysis.

¹ 'Anonymity' refers to the email address of the applicant in the Wellcome Trust database being recorded as anon@wellcome.org.uk

A hazard rate analysis was performed as the nature of the data is right-censored (i.e. those submitting in 2018 do not have a chance to reapply, whereas those submitting in 2009 had 9 years to re-apply). Hazard rate analysis is a non-parametric tool that is used to estimate the cumulative number of expected events (reapplication).

The sample was further broken down into two groups; (Group 1) whether the application at T_0 submitted was successful ($n=680$); or (Group 2) whether the application at T_0 was rejected ($n=2709$). The results showed that both groups had the same pattern in their hazard rate, that is, a relatively constant increase in reapplication rates per year. The reapplication rate for the first year as found to be 21% if the application was successful (Group 1) and 7.8% if unsuccessful (Group 2). The yearly increase in reapplication rate was 9% per year for those with a successful application at T_0 (Group 1), and 3.6% per year for Group 2. After 7 years, 75% of the successful applicants at T_0 re-applied for funding from either Wellcome or other funding agencies, whereas only 20.5% of the unsuccessful applicants at T_0 reapplied.

Future analysis plans

At the moment, this study is in progress and the analysis incomplete. The research group has access to a linguistic analysis of reviewer reports as well as the publication-level data for $n=4105$ successful and unsuccessful applicants. The initial plans are to broaden and further refine the hazard rate analysis and the factors underpinning of the likelihood to resubmit for the entire sample. This also includes the characteristics of the feedback received by applicants as reported in Derrick et al (2022), or other demographic, personal (resilience) or else institutional capacity variables. Towards this ongoing goal, we welcome feedback and interested parties who may be open to collaborating with the next stage of the analysis.

Discussion

The results showed that 50% of unsuccessful applicants at T_0 reapplied at T_1 , with 35% of these achieving success with this reapplication. This provides an opportunity for future research focusing on this analytical space to understand the function of peer review and the effect that an applicant's experience with peer review, may play in their likelihood of pursuing a research career within academic and/or resubmitting a future funding application.

This provides an opportunity to expand the understanding of peer review as it is currently conceptualised away from solely a selection tool, to one that can more holistically mobilise peer reviewer reports to act as feedback towards improving submissions and increasing the potential for success at T_1 (participation/development). This re-imagining of peer review would also work to support applicants to persist in their academic careers and/or develop their research agenda even in the event of an unsuccessful outcome. Considering that within the current peer review decision-making processes that the majority of applicants are unsuccessful, extending the function of peer review to include stronger developmental and participation elements could have wide ranging benefits to how research culture supports researcher generally, as well as at the early stages of their careers.

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